

Original Research Article

Exploring Teachers' Fears and Resistance when Learning about Culturally Responsive Pedagogy in the Mathematics Classroom

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ABSTRACT: In this study, we examine the fears and resistance of prospective and practicing teachers (PPTs) toward culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP) in mathematics classrooms. Drawing on reflective journal assignments collected during several offerings of a teacher education course in Canada, we ground our analysis in Ladson-Billings' elements of a culturally relevant pedagogy and extend it through our COFRI model (Challenges, Opportunities, Fears, Resistance, Insights). Our use of thematic analysis with PPTs' reflections reveals that PPTs experience mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological fears, alongside forms of resistance which can also be categorized as mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological. These PPT-expressed fears and resistance serve as barriers to developing one's CRP, highlighting tensions between personal and professional identity, systemic constraints, and the complexities of implementing CRP. To address these barriers, we introduce reflective praxis tools that encourage PPTs to confront and navigate their fears and resistance. Through this research, we aim to advance understandings of CRP in mathematics education and offer actionable strategies for promoting equitable and culturally responsive teaching practices.

KEYWORDS: *fears, resistance, culturally responsive pedagogy, mathematics, prospective and practicing teachers*

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Broadly speaking, culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP) is an approach emphasizing the importance of making connections between school curricula and learners' sociocultural situations. In acknowledging that mathematics teachers' knowledge, beliefs, and practices are culturally situated (Andrews, 2009; Xenofontos et al., 2024), we see CRP as a pedagogical approach that underscores the links between culture and the teaching/learning of school subjects. Although varied versions of pedagogy in relation to culture appear across the literature, our use of CRP here refers to culturally *responsive* pedagogy.

In this paper, we outline the progression of a CRP course-based research study (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, b, c), where our aim was to analyze the perspectives on CRP that prospective and practicing teachers (PPTs) brought to a university teacher education course on CRP in the mathematics classroom. That is, we aimed to explore how PPTs interpreted the social, cultural and political challenges of teaching through CRP. In doing so, we trace the conceptual development of a framework of five integral components of PPTs' perspectives on CRP in mathematics: challenges, opportunities, fears, resistance, and insights (COFRI). The study, conducted over several offerings of the CRP course, gathered data in the form of a reflective journal assignment where participants (PPTs) were asked to respond daily to questions designed to stimulate their growth and development of CRP. In this paper, while we report generally on the development and implementation of COFRI, we attend to a more specific focus on unpacking and analyzing the study's data through the lens of two specific COFRI components: fear (F) and resistance (R).

While the research study was conducted at a Canadian university, the implications for the field of mathematics education and teacher education extend well beyond this context. Before we turn our attention to the relevant international literature that helped us frame our work, we first conceptually trace the development of our COFRI framework. Subsequently, we present our findings and discuss implications and future directions of our work.

Conceptual Development of COFRI Framework

In our work with the course data, we began by adopting the theoretical model developed by Ladson-Billings (1995) (where CRP, in her work, stands for culturally *relevant* pedagogy). Even though Ladson-Billings's (1995a, 1995b) original theory was termed culturally *relevant* pedagogy, through its varied implementation and execution, other terms have since been proposed in the research, each with its own focus and set of intentions. For example, culturally *responsive* pedagogy was initially defined by Gay (2010) as "using cultural knowledge, prior experiences, frames of reference, and performance styles of ethnically diverse students to make learning encounters more relevant to and effective for them" (p. 31). One can notice even within this definition that Gay's *responsive* work closely connects to Ladson-Billings' *relevant* work. On the other hand, two additional terms commonly found in more recent research are culturally *sustaining* pedagogies (Alim & Paris, 2017; Paris, 2012) and culturally *revitalising* pedagogies (McCarty & Lee 2014), both of which claim to go beyond being responsive and relevant to the cultural experiences of students. In a focus on *sustaining*, Paris (2012) proposes the need "to perpetuate and foster—to sustain—linguistic, literate, and cultural pluralism as part of the democratic project of schooling" (p. 95), whereas McCarty and Lee (2014) extend sustaining practices into a specific Indigenous focus, proposing a sustaining/revitalizing focus which "recognizes the need to reclaim and revitalize what has been disrupted and displaced by colonization" (p. 103). Both of these culture-focused pedagogies aim to extend and critique earlier work by Gay and Ladson-Billings. Notwithstanding the benefits of these more critical approaches, the research context for the study described in this paper is a course in culturally responsive pedagogy in the mathematics classroom; hence, our use of CRP reflects

the *responsive* work of Gay, while also embracing the closely related elements of Ladson-Billings' *relevant* work.

Ladson-Billings (2006) proposes there are three elements to CRP: academic achievement - AA (also called student learning), cultural competence - CC, and sociopolitical consciousness - SC. The widespread adoption of her theoretical model is due in no small part to her aim of reframing 'how we think' (Ladson-Billings 2006, p. 30) as educators: 'Instead of the specific lessons and activities that we select to fill the day, we must begin to understand the ways our theories and philosophies are made to manifest in the pedagogical practices and rationales we exhibit in the classroom' (p. 30).

As discussed in Nolan and Xenofontos (2023a), we began analyzing our study's data by adopting Ladson-Billings' three CRP elements. Having noted limited application of her work in mathematics education research, we wanted to explore how the three elements could be used with data specific to mathematics. We initiated our qualitative thematic analysis by viewing data through the lens of these three separate elements, but soon realised how the data reflected intersections and overlaps among the elements. This led us to conceptualise our CRP Venn diagram (Figure 1i) to illustrate the seven categories (or areas) created when all three elements and their overlaps were considered.

Figure 1. The Process of Reconceptualizing CRP and Conceptualizing COFRI

Classifying PPTs' perspectives in one of these seven areas of the Venn diagram still presented many challenges. We realized that it might not be productive to try to distinguish between the elements, since the boundaries between them were not so clear (Figure 1ii). While the inseparability of the elements was a significant insight for us, what came to the forefront was how PPTs' perspectives had specific characteristics associated with them. For example, some responses expressed *challenges* associated with enacting CRP, while others appeared to express *fear* or *resistance* to CRP. In fact, when we re-examined the data with a different lens—one that specifically sought to identify and describe the types of characteristics being expressed—we concluded that there are five underlying characteristics within their responses, which describe or qualify their perspectives toward CRP. We label these as *challenge*, *opportunity*, *fear*, *resistance*, and *insight* (COFRI), and see them as framed by Ladson-Billings' CRP elements (Figure 1iii). In other words, we built upon Ladson-Billings' theoretical work to develop a new framework, which we refer to as COFRI, to highlight those five integral characteristics, or components, of PPTs' perspectives on CRP (see Table 1). By drawing on that framework and PPTs' initial responses in the CRP course reflective journal assignment (first two entries only), we analyzed the perspectives of five PPTs enrolled in that CRP course, presenting them as a series of participant narrative case studies (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023b).

Characteristic	Brief Description
<i>Challenge</i>	The idea of challenge involves awareness of one's lack or partial development of competence to address an issue. Challenge is based on a person's perception that new knowledge, dispositions, skills, or tools (KDST) are required, which they are inspired to move forward and acquire.
<i>Opportunity</i>	Opportunity refers to the identification of space for something "good" to happen. A person sees the space as already existing; things are in place to move forward (i.e., the person has the KDST to move forward) to make good things happen.
<i>Fear</i>	The feeling that attempting something might lead to failure. A person might be inclined to stop in their tracks (or even move backward), and to rationalise this (non)movement by saying they do not have (and cannot easily obtain) the KDST to achieve it.
<i>Resistance</i>	The expression of dispositions against or disbelief in the importance, feasibility, or possibility of specific ideas. Resistance can manifest itself through "rationalising discourses" which have the property of projecting how <i>others</i> will act or respond to a situation—an "it's not me, it's them" approach to resisting an idea.
<i>Insight</i>	An understanding or realization of what is currently happening and/or how things could be. In addition to seeing what is currently happening, a person will generate new ideas for extending, adapting, and/or improving. Generally, when a person has 'insight', this will affect the other four components. That is, an insight suggests a new direction which could create a new challenge, opportunity or even fear or resistance depending on the 'tools' one has. Consequently, an insight might lead to gaining new tools (challenge), moving forward with what one has (opportunity), halting/moving backwards (fear), or disbelief (resistance).

Table 1. *The (Original) COFRI Framework – Brief Description of Components (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, p. 562)*

As we sought to build upon these findings, and essentially 'test' our COFRI framework on the remaining journal responses for these same five case study participants, we noticed interesting relationships between the five components that had not been evident in our initial analysis. This ultimately lead us toward a desire to dig more deeply into each of the individual components, while also exploring how the components interacted and intersected with each other in interesting and unexpected ways. Our aim of taking this deep look at each component began for us with the component of *insight* (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023c), where we reflected on the ways in which specific types of insights are connected to the other four components in PPTs' reflections throughout this semester-long CRP course. In doing so, we were able to revise our original definition for *insight*, which now included the identification of three different types of CRP-related insights (mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological) in PPTs' journal entries as a result of their engagement with the course. Our revised definition for insight is as follows:

An understanding or realization of what is currently happening and/or how things could be. In addition to seeing what is currently happening, a person will generate new ideas for

extending, adapting, and/or improving. In general, insights can be (1) connected to one or more of the other four components (challenge, opportunity, fear, or resistance), and (2) classified as a specific type (mathematical, pedagogical, or ideological). That is, an insight suggests a new direction which either emerges from or leads into a challenge, opportunity or even fear or resistance depending on the 'tools' one has. Consequently, an insight might connect to gaining new tools (challenge), moving forward with what one has (opportunity), halting/moving backwards (fear), or disbelief (resistance) and, in each case, typically highlights aspects of mathematics subject matter, mathematics pedagogy, or one's ideological/sociopolitical perspectives on mathematics.

Since the process of scrutinizing and expanding the definitions for each individual component is still underway, we do not yet offer a fully revised COFRI framework/table. It is, in fact, the aim of this paper to present an analysis of the study's data for these same five case study participants through the lenses of *fear* (F) and *resistance* (R), so that we might offer additional details on, and insight into, how we initially defined these components in COFRI (see Table 1). We propose that our extended work on fear and resistance in this paper presents strong data-driven support for the use of the COFRI framework for our own study and for other studies seeking to understand and grow PPTs' perspectives on CRP in mathematics classrooms.

Fears and Resistance in Teacher Education: An Exploration of the Areas

Teacher education is often fraught with various fears and forms of resistance that can significantly impact the effectiveness and confidence of prospective and practising teachers (PPTs). These fears and resistances encompass both general anxieties experienced across all subjects and those specific to teaching mathematics. They are multifaceted and interconnected, necessitating a comprehensive understanding and approach in addressing them (Archer, 2022; Butler & Yendol-Hoppey, 2024). In the following pages, we review the literature on fears and resistance in teacher education, first in relation to general teacher education and then with specific references to mathematics teacher education. This review serves to support and frame our work in the area of culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP), specifically in relation to our COFRI framework.

Fears in Teacher Education

One of the most pervasive concerns among PPTs is the fear of incompetence and failure (Breen, 2001; Vithal, 2003). Many teacher candidates worry they are insufficiently prepared or knowledgeable, leading to a significant lack of confidence in their teaching abilities. This anxiety is often exacerbated by concerns about classroom management, where maintaining discipline and managing classroom dynamics are major sources of stress (Ashton & Arlington, 2019; Bates, et al. 2013; Hong & Greene, 2011). The disconnect between theoretical knowledge and practical application is another significant source of anxiety. PPTs often struggle to integrate pedagogical theories into real classroom settings, leading to fears about their ability to teach effectively (Latta, 2005).

Additionally, many PPTs feel isolated and unsupported within their teacher education programmes, experiencing marginalisation and a lack of community, which further intensifies their fears (Brown, 2014; Vithal, 2003). Professional isolation and lack of support have been reported by PPTs. This fear of being isolated within their professional environments intensifies PPTs' concerns about incompetence, controversial topics, and diverse classrooms. Building a supportive community within teacher education programmes is essential to mitigating these fears (Brown,

2014; Vithal, 2003). The unpredictability of classroom situations and the unknown aspects of teaching contribute significantly to teacher anxiety. This fear of the unknown creates a sense of uncertainty that hinders teachers' ability to effectively plan and execute lessons (Ashton & Arlington, 2019; Huma, 2014; Robinson & Goodey, 2018). Concerns about personal and professional identity are also prevalent, with teachers worrying about their perception as competent and effective educators (Griffin, 2015; Stoehr, 2017).

Addressing controversial topics such as social justice, race, and LGBTQ+ issues adds another layer of fear for PPTs. The potential backlash from parents, colleagues, and the community can discourage teachers from engaging with these essential yet sensitive subjects (Baily & Katradis, 2016; Bender-Slack, 2010; Meyer et al., 2019). Furthermore, the fear of inadequate preparation for teaching diverse student populations is a significant concern. Teachers often feel unprepared to handle the cultural and linguistic diversity they will encounter in their classrooms, leading to anxiety about their ability to effectively reach and teach all students (Brown, 2014; Gay & Howard, 2000).

These fears intersect across multiple dimensions, highlighting the complex nature of PPTs' anxieties. For example, the fear of incompetence can manifest in various subject areas (e.g., general teaching, mathematics, social justice.) and settings (e.g., inclusive classrooms, diverse student populations). Additionally, systemic and institutional pressures, such as not aligning with institutional policies or community expectations, can significantly impact how teachers approach controversial topics and manage their classrooms (Bender-Slack, 2010; Huma, 2014). Teachers' own backgrounds and identities also play a crucial role in their fears. PPTs of colour, for instance, may feel marginalised within their programmes and worry about their ability to handle diverse classrooms effectively (Brown, 2014). Personal negative experiences with subjects like mathematics can deeply affect teachers' confidence and teaching approaches (Itter & Meyers, 2017). Furthermore, fears of burnout and emotional resilience in general teaching are prevalent concerns (Shoyer & Leshem, 2016).

PPTs also worry about negative student reactions and engagement. Concerns about students' pre-existing negative attitudes toward certain subjects and the challenge of engaging them effectively are significant sources of anxiety (Bates et al., 2013; Shoyer & Leshem, 2016). Additionally, fears related to cultural and social barriers, such as addressing the cultural and linguistic diversity in their classrooms adequately (Gay & Howard, 2000) and confronting personal biases in racially diverse settings, further compound these anxieties (Vithal, 2003). Concerns about professional identity and development are also common. For instance, prospective teachers often fear not being seen as "real" teachers (McGlynn-Stewart, 2010) and struggle with professional esteem and self-efficacy, especially when dealing with inclusive education (Robinson & Goodey, 2018). Legal and professional fears can deter teachers from addressing controversial topics. Concerns about backlash, legal implications, and job security often lead to self-censorship and a cautious approach to curriculum design (Meyer et al., 2019).

Fears in Mathematics Teacher Education. In addition to these general fears, PPTs often experience specific fears related to teaching mathematics. Many teachers feel they lack sufficient understanding of mathematical concepts, which undermines their confidence in teaching the subject (Bates et al., 2013; Breen, 2001; Itter & Meyers, 2017; Lutovac & Kaasila, 2014). This is closely linked to the fear of teaching mathematics effectively, where teachers worry about their ability to address varying student abilities and ensure student engagement (Bates et al., 2013; McGlynn-Stewart, 2010; Stoehr, 2017). Teachers also fear the negative attitudes students may already have toward mathematics. Concerns about students' pre-existing dislike of mathematics and the challenge of engaging them are significant (Bates et al., 2013; Lutovac & Kaasila, 2014).

Emotional and psychological aspects related to mathematical experiences significantly contribute to teachers' fears. Negative past experiences with mathematics can create a persistent sense of anxiety and inadequacy (Itter & Meyers, 2017), exacerbating their current fears about teaching the subject (Breen, 2001; Stoehr, 2017). Public failure and embarrassment are also common fears among mathematics PPTs. The prospect of being embarrassed or failing publicly in a subject they struggled with themselves is daunting (Breen, 2001; Itter & Meyers, 2017). This fear is often linked to concerns about not having enough effective teaching methods or ideas to teach mathematics successfully (Bates et al., 2013; McGlynn-Stewart, 2010).

Resistance in Teacher Education

Resistance in teacher education is a complex issue that deeply affects the engagement and adaptability of PPTs. This resistance comes from various sources, including teaching methods, personal beliefs, and the broader context in which they work. Understanding and addressing these challenges is crucial for effective intervention.

One common type of resistance among PPTs is pedagogical resistance. This often stems from uncertainty and a lack of confidence in using new teaching strategies, especially those that differ from traditional methods (Aguirre et al., 2012; Harris & Lázár, 2011). For example, teachers frequently express doubts about integrating culturally responsive teaching into their practices, questioning its relevance and feasibility (cite one of our papers). Another significant barrier is ideological resistance, rooted deeply in the beliefs and values of PPTs. This includes scepticism about the need to include social justice and multicultural education in their teaching. Many teachers believe that traditional methods are sufficient and see new approaches as unnecessary or unsuitable, especially for younger students (Bronkhorst et al., 2014). As Rodriguez (2005a) points out, ideological resistance is often entrenched in long-standing educational norms. Personal and emotional resistance also plays a crucial role. Teachers often resist change due to fear and anxiety about their ability to effectively use new methods. This resistance can show up as reluctance to engage with new teaching approaches or outright opposition to curricular reforms (Dinkelman, 2009; Samuel, 2014). For example, fear of professional repercussions can lead PPTs to avoid using culturally relevant teaching practices despite recognising their importance (Neri et al., 2019).

Resistance can appear in both active and passive forms. Active resistance includes vocal opposition to new teaching methods or curriculum changes, such as organising petitions or expressing frustration during discussions (Nicol, 2006). Totto et al. (2006) note that these behaviours are common when new initiatives are introduced without adequate support. Passive resistance, on the other hand, might involve minimal participation in reflective practices or superficial adherence to new teaching requirements without genuine engagement (Hsieh & Nguyen, 2021; Shim, 2018). For example, in multicultural education, PPTs may resist by adopting colour-blind ideologies, insisting on the sameness of all students, and dismissing the importance of cultural differences. This undermines the goals of multicultural education by failing to recognise and address the unique needs of diverse students (Rose & Potts, 2011).

Resistance in Mathematics Teacher Education. In mathematics teacher education, resistance often manifests as a reluctance to adopt non-traditional teaching methods. Teachers may express discomfort with problem-solving approaches, questioning their practicality and acceptance by headteachers and parents (Nicol, 2006). This resistance is compounded by concerns about effectively teaching mathematical concepts in ways that engage all pupils (Breen, 2001; Itter & Meyers, 2017). Specifically, resistance towards culturally responsive teaching can be significant (LaDuke, 2009; Nolan, 2023; Tinkler & Tinkler, 2013). Teachers may hesitate to integrate culturally diverse examples and perspectives into their mathematics curriculum, fearing it could complicate lesson plans or be perceived as less rigorous. This reluctance is often driven by a lack of familiarity

with pupils' cultural backgrounds and uncertainty about how to meaningfully connect these to mathematical concepts (Xenofontos, 2016) and to do so in ways that do not lead to cultural appropriation (one of our papers?). Additionally, institutional constraints, such as standardised testing requirements and prescribed curricula, may leave teachers feeling constrained in their ability to implement culturally responsive practices. As a result, despite evidence that such approaches can enhance student engagement and understanding, resistance at both the individual and systemic levels can pose significant challenges to their adoption and effectiveness (Nolan & Keazer, 2021).

The resistance patterns seen among PPTs highlight the complex interplay between personal beliefs, institutional pressures, and the perceived relevance of new teaching methods. Resistance often arises from a perceived gap between the theoretical concepts taught in teacher education programmes and the practical realities of classroom teaching (Rodriguez 2005b). The gap between traditional teaching methods and new approaches can lead to scepticism about the effectiveness of innovative teaching strategies. This highlights the urgent need to bridge this gap in order to support teachers in accepting and implementing innovative teaching methods (Thomas & Vanderhaaro, 2008).

Addressing Fears and Resistance

Addressing PPTs' fears and resistance in teacher education requires a comprehensive approach, including additional support and training to build confidence and competence in new teaching methods. Teacher education programmes need to create opportunities for PPTs to engage meaningfully with diverse teaching approaches through well-structured assignments and reflective practices (Aguirre et al., 2012; Hara & Sherbine, 2018). Moreover, fostering a supportive and inclusive community within teacher education programmes can help reduce resistance by addressing the emotional and psychological aspects of change. Building a culture of openness and collaboration encourages teachers to embrace new methods and effectively integrate them into their teaching practices (Brown, 2014; Vithal, 2003). To sum up, the interconnected nature of fears and resistance in teacher education in general, and in mathematics teacher education more specifically, highlights the need for a multifaceted and supportive approach to preparing teachers for the complexities of the classroom. Through comprehensive support systems and reflective practices, teacher education programs can better prepare future educators to navigate and excel in their professional journeys. As illustrated in this paper, one way forward toward introducing supportive and reflective practices could be through a reflective framework known as COFRI (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, b, c).

Methodology

Research Context and Participants

As already discussed, this study builds upon our earlier work examining PPTs' perspectives on culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP) in mathematics education (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, b, c). The data were collected as part of a course titled *Culturally Responsive Pedagogy in the Mathematics Classroom*, offered within the Teaching Elementary School Mathematics (TESM) certificate program at a Canadian university. Designed to deepen understanding of mathematical concepts while cultivating critical cultural consciousness, the course integrates research from intersecting fields such as ethnomathematics, Indigenous education, critical mathematics education, and equity-based research (Nolan, 2023; Nolan & Keazer, 2021).

Across three offerings of the course (2017, 2019, and 2021), 38 PPTs participated, with 31 consenting to have their reflective journals analyzed as part of this research. In keeping with our previous work (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, b, c), this paper focuses on five case study

participants – Cindy, Olive, Felix, Raymond, and Iris (pseudonyms) – whose reflective journal responses illustrate diverse and nuanced engagements with CRP. These five participants were selected to ensure consistency and depth of analysis, as their responses have been analyzed in prior papers and provide rich data for exploring fears and resistance.

Data Collection and Analysis

The primary data source for this study was a reflective journal assignment completed during the course. Participants were asked to respond daily to prompts designed to elicit their evolving understandings of CRP. These prompts included questions such as, “*What concerns or excites you the most about bringing culture, responsiveness, and mathematics together?*” and “*How do you differentiate between culturally appropriate and cultural appropriation?*” As a data collection method, reflective journaling aligns with prior research emphasizing the importance of personal reflection in developing culturally responsive practices (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, b, c; Rychly & Graves, 2012).

Data analysis took place in two sequentially organized phases. In the first phase, we aimed to identify patterns in PPTs’ expressions of fears and resistance across their reflective journal entries from all three course offerings. Following Braun and Clarke’s (2022) approach to thematic analysis, we began with open coding to identify recurring themes and subsequently employed axial coding to organize these themes into categories. This process was guided by the original working definitions of fear and resistance from the COFRI framework (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, b, c), along with our findings from the previous in-depth analysis of the *insight* component of COFRI. In other words, our thematic analysis was shaped by a lens formed through our earlier refinement of the *insight* component of COFRI (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023c). In that paper, our findings describe three types of insights: mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological. For the sake of continuity and consistency across our framework components, our analysis of the data to refine the descriptions of *fear* and *resistance* maintains this focus: we have viewed our data through this 3-part lens, identifying what we determine to be mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological fears and resistance. Further clarification of this approach is provided in the Findings section. In Table 2, we use “fears” and “resistance” as our broad themes and then present the three types or categories of each. We also provide a hypothetical quote for each category to help illustrate how the category is defined.

In the second phase, we focused specifically on the five case study participants to maintain continuity with our earlier work. By revisiting their reflective journal entries, we applied the categories identified in phase 1 to analyze their expressions of fear and resistance in greater depth. This approach allowed us to explore the interplay between these components and how they manifested in the context of CRP. Our previous work established the importance of narrative case studies in preserving the richness of individual perspectives and highlighting the intersections among COFRI components (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a, b, c).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the university’s research ethics board. Participants provided informed consent to have their journal entries included in the research. All names used in the analysis are pseudonyms to protect participant confidentiality.

To ensure the trustworthiness of our findings, we adhered to established qualitative research practices. Triangulation was achieved by analyzing data across three course offerings and revisiting previously studied participants to ensure consistency in findings (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Both authors independently coded the data before engaging in collaborative discussions to reconcile differences and refine the thematic categories (Boyatzis, 1998). The use of rich, illustrative quotes from participants’ journal entries further enhanced the credibility and confirmability of the analysis.

Finally, maintaining detailed audit trails throughout the coding and analysis process ensured transparency and dependability in the study's methodological approach.

Findings

Building on our earlier COFRI-based analysis of the "insight" component, we approached the thematic analysis with a focus shaped by those prior findings. Specifically, we examined the journal data through the lens of three potential forms of fear and resistance: mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological. Each of these is inherently intertwined with cultural aspects, given the nature of the course and the data collected. We consider these three categories sufficiently broad to be identifiable in our own findings and in other teachers' or teacher educators' applications of the COFRI framework, while also distinct enough to be differentiated across various students and contexts.

Fears

PPTs' fears related to CRP have been organized into the three main categories: of mathematical fears; pedagogical fears; and ideological fears. Below, we present each with the use of illustrative quotes from PPTs' reflective journal entries. It is important to add that for each category, whether mathematical, pedagogical or ideological, the fears we write about are in the context of the course on CRP in mathematics classrooms; in other words, each category of fear is understood to exist within the context of studying culture and mathematics. For example, a mathematical fear is generally not about the content of mathematics itself but reflects a fear around developing knowledge and skills in relation to both culture and mathematics.

Mathematical Fears. Mathematical fears pertain to the PPTs' own subject-matter knowledge in the context of CRP, and can manifest in various forms. These include fear of insufficient knowledge (e.g., "My mathematics is not good") or fear of inadequate preparation (e.g., "I have not been prepared well"). In this respect, Raymond raises a significant concern about the mathematical challenges involved in integrating cultural responsiveness into teaching. His reflection emphasizes a fear of inadequacy in crafting meaningful mathematical questions that preserve both mathematical rigor and cultural authenticity. This tension reflects the difficulty of balancing complex, multi-level mathematical inquiry with an authentic respect for cultural contexts, while avoiding oversimplification or misrepresentation.

When I look for things that are concerning or exciting about bringing culture, responsiveness, and math together, I'm afraid I mostly come up with concerns. Which is a concern in itself, I suppose. It feels like such an enormous goal, and I'm worried I'll find myself reluctant to begin. When I consider the textbook examples of 'cultural math' that we saw in class today, it was easy to identify that some math questions were good math questions (rich, multi-level, extendable, connection-building scenarios), and some were more trivial (requiring low-level cognitive processes, or simple repetition of algorithm). I found that my impulse was to identify 'good' math questions as 'good cultural math' questions. But I can see that even the 'good' questions tended to mathematize (trivialize) the cultures in question rather than explore that culture's approach to math.

Raymond's journal entry exemplifies the challenges PPTs face in distinguishing meaningful mathematical tasks from those that risk trivializing cultural contexts. This concern highlights the intricate interplay between maintaining mathematical depth and addressing broader educational objectives.

Themes	Sub-themes and categories, with “hypothetical quotes” for the category
Fears	<p>Mathematical fears: Concerns about subject-matter knowledge, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of insufficient knowledge: “My mathematics is not good” • Fear of inadequate preparation: “I have not been prepared well” <hr/> <p>Pedagogical fears: Concerns about translating knowledge into effective teaching practices, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of inadequate implementation: “What if I don’t manage to do it?” • Fear of complexity: “What if I encounter unexpected issues?” • Fear of causing harm: “I’m worried I may not be able to support students’ learning” <hr/> <p>Ideological fears: Apprehensions about engaging with diverse cultural contexts, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of cultural appropriation: “What if I inadvertently appropriate a culture?” • Fear of cultural insensitivity: “What if I am disrespectful?” • Fear of misrepresentation: “What if I misrepresent a culture?”
Resistance*	<p>Mathematical resistance: Resistance framed in relation to mathematics content or curriculum, often expressed as external barriers that make CRP seem impractical. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projection onto others: “Students/parents won’t accept this kind of math” • Systemic constraints: “The curriculum leaves no room for cultural connections in math” • Feasibility concerns (time, overloaded curricula): “There isn’t enough time in math class to add culture” • Lack of resources or models: “There aren’t enough examples of cultural math tasks to use” <hr/> <p>Pedagogical resistance: Skepticism about the effectiveness or necessity of CRP, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preference for traditional methods: “Why CRP since we know that our methods work well?” • Doubt in CRP’s effectiveness: “I’m not convinced it works” • Attachment to familiar practices: “CRP sounds good in theory, but my way works in practice” <hr/> <p>Ideological resistance: Rooted in deeply held beliefs, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to ideological change: “We shouldn’t change our ways because of people’s diverse backgrounds” • Belief in the cultural neutrality of mathematics: “Mathematics is mathematics” • Disbelief in CRP’s relevance: “My students don’t have diverse backgrounds; I don’t see the point in this”

* These categories (mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological) are offered as analytic lenses to highlight different dimensions of resistance. In practice, however, the boundaries between them are porous. Most examples reflect more than one type: a concern about time, for instance, may be both mathematical (curriculum demands) and pedagogical (instructional choices), while a statement such as “mathematics is mathematics” is ideological but also shapes pedagogical preferences and assumptions about mathematical content. The categories should therefore be read as intersecting rather than mutually exclusive, with each example placed under one category for analytic clarity.

Table 2. *Fears and Resistance – Findings from Thematic Analysis*

Pedagogical Fears. Pedagogical fears arise from concerns about transforming knowledge into effective teaching practices that promote student learning. These fears may include apprehensions about inadequate implementation (e.g., “What if I don’t manage to do it?”), the complexity of certain teaching methods (e.g., “What if I encounter unexpected issues?”), and causing unintended harm (e.g., “I’m worried I may not be able to support students’ learning”). For example, Iris reflects on her personal experiences and background, expressing anxiety about embedding different cultural perspectives in the classroom.

I definitely feel a level of concern and anxiety in embedding different cultures into the classroom. I hope this is taken as me expressing my vulnerability rather than ignorance and privilege, but I grew up in a predominantly white, upper-middle-class community. My exposure to any culture different than that of my own was not overly emphasized, same with my understanding of any social/economic injustices as well. Now to be teaching in the exact same community, I do fear that I will often ‘come up short’ in delivering enriched lessons in cultural diversity (for one, but along with many other branches including social justice). This, especially, coming on the heels of a very educational and eye-opening year where I had to readdress my understanding of my privilege after many amazing movements across Canada and the US. In summation, I think I worry that I have been raised with a very Eurocentric worldview and although I have addressed that over the years, I worry about my effectiveness in teaching about other cultures in an authentic way that is appropriate, and not appropriation.

Iris’s comments shed light on the tension PPTs experience between personal growth and professional readiness. Her apprehensions stem from a genuine desire to teach authentically and respectfully, despite limitations in her lived experiences. This reflects a broader fear that highlights the need for PPTs to balance personal identity, cultural sensitivity, and pedagogical effectiveness. Cindy’s perspective similarly illustrates the fear of causing harm through lessons that do not dig deeply enough or provide enough background information. Her fear was based in acknowledging that it is important to “not only appreciate the culture but understand the meaning and significance of the activity... Surface level lessons can still be beneficial, but are students really getting that deeper understanding?”

Put together, the reflections of both Iris and Cindy illustrate the intricate challenges PPTs face when navigating their fears around the intersection of pedagogy, culture, and their own experience, pointing towards the importance of self-reflection, intentional learning, and collaborative efforts to ensure both effective teaching and equitable education.

Ideological Fears. Ideological fears emerge from the challenges associated with engaging thoughtfully and meaningfully with the diverse cultures represented in classrooms, critical engagement with CRP concepts, and rethinking dominant narratives in mathematics education. Such fears often center around concerns of cultural appropriation, insensitivity, or misrepresentation. If guided toward self-reflection, these fears could reflect key moments of professional, epistemological, and personal transformation for PPTs. For instance, Olive comments on incorporating cultural content into mathematics teaching, revealing apprehensions about using tokenism or unintentionally causing harm.

I am no expert on culture, immediately my mind went to, ‘How do I ensure I am not using tokenism?’ which I see frequently done with treaty education. This is most definitely the

start of something new for me, as I traditionally have seen math as a $1+1=2$, step-by-step, sequential, one way to get the answer, kind of subject.

Her apprehension is further revealed when she considers her approach to Indigenous content, saying, "I myself, know that when approaching Indigenous content, I often begin to wonder, 'What if I do something or say something wrong?'" These reflections highlight the fear of unintentionally causing harm through misrepresentation or by reinforcing stereotypes. For PPTs, this fear can create a significant barrier when attempting to incorporate cultural perspectives in an authentic way.

Felix adds another layer to these challenges, reflecting on his position and the weight of responsibility that comes with it. He shares,

I think my concerns weigh heavily on me and make it difficult to get excited. I try to be reflective of my privilege and place in addressing social inequity as a white man in modern society. I have often struggled with my place in this narrative, and how I can appropriately uplift the voices of those who need to be heard without overstepping or filling the cliché 'nice white person' role. Concisely, I am concerned about doing a poor job of bringing culture, responsiveness, and mathematics together and similarly concerned not doing ANY job out of fear of doing it poorly.

Iris, commenting on her classroom readings, explains how cultural integration in teaching has added to her apprehensions. In her own words,

After day one of EMTH 425 we read Wiest's article 'Teaching Mathematics from a Multicultural Perspective. Equity & Excellence in Education' where she referenced a quote from Zaslavsky (1993): "Teachers must be careful that they do not introduce cultural applications as examples of "quaint customs" or "primitive practices." These applications must form an integral part of the mathematics curriculum. They must inspire students to think critically about the reasons for these practices, to dig deeply into the lives and environment of the people involved. It is so easy to trivialize the concept of multicultural education by throwing in a few examples as holidays approach. Better not to do it at all!" This quote was pretty alarming to me, specifically because I had started this class so eagerly and excitedly that when I read 'do it right or don't do it at all,' I became quite apprehensive.

Overall, these reflections demonstrate the deep concerns PPTs face when addressing cultural diversity in their classrooms. Whether navigating the risks of misrepresentation, grappling with privilege, or fearing tokenism, the shared apprehension is rooted in a desire to teach with authenticity and respect.

Resistance

Here we discuss how PPTs expressed resistance to CRP according to the three different types identified: mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological. While these categories provide a useful framework for analysis, distinguishing between them when it relates to the component of resistance is not always straightforward. Individual reflections often contain elements that overlap categories, and readers may recognize aspects of other types within a given quote. Examples from the five PPTs' journal entries are used to illustrate these dynamics, showing how resistance is shaped by both external circumstances and personal perspectives.

Mathematical Resistance. For these PPTs, resistance to implementing CRP was often manifested in relation to mathematics or mathematics curriculum, where challenges are externalized or attributed to systemic and practical barriers. This category of resistance often takes the form of rationalizing discourses, in statements like, “It’s not me, it’s how things are,” and can be expressed through projection onto others, systemic constraints, feasibility concerns, or a lack of resources. Projection onto others allows PPTs to shift responsibility for challenges onto colleagues, parents, or students. This form of rationalization distances PPTs from personal accountability and frames the barriers to CRP as external. Similarly, systemic constraints are a common rationale, with PPTs pointing to the rigidity of the school system, mandated curriculum requirements, and institutional policies as obstacles. This fosters a sense of powerlessness, reflected in the sentiment, “It’s not me, it’s how the school system works.” Practical concerns, such as time constraints and an overloaded curriculum, also contribute to resistance. PPTs often feel that integrating CRP is simply not feasible within their current schedules and workloads. This sense of impossibility is further compounded by what they perceive as a lack of access to adequate resources or professional development, leaving PPTs feeling unprepared and unsupported to meet the expectations of CRP.

Olive reflects on the pressures of systemic constraints and the curriculum, explaining,

Being a teacher, with many responsibilities and demands, it is hard to imagine adding one more thing to the pot per say. The first concern that came to mind was, of course, the curriculum. A document that has been forced, squished, and squeezed since the second I entered the doors of the university upon my educational journey.

She elaborates further on the difficulty of aligning CRP with curriculum demands, stating,

As teachers, we are mandated to teach certain outcome driven concepts of mathematics, which can be challenging to complete within a school year. It would take thoughtful and timely planning to apply these concepts effectively without taking away from math time and staying inline with the curriculum. With the many demands on a teacher already, this appears to be an extremely overwhelming task, without proper support or PD in the area, it may be nearly impossible.

Cindy, for example, grapples with the challenges of introducing social justice themes into early-grade classrooms, stating,

I still have a hard time seeing [social justice] in a K/1/2 classroom which is the lens I have been looking at things through as these are the grades I will be teaching this fall. After looking at some of the topics that can be covered under the social justice umbrella such as domestic violence and an overabundance of liquor stores in the community, I do not see how these ideas can be incorporated into these younger grades.

Cindy also voices concerns about the overwhelming scope of teaching cultural diversity:

One thing that concerns me is the sheer amount of cultures that there are in the world and how on Earth am I going to do them all justice when teaching students... There are just so many different cultures that it would be a lot for us as teachers as we would have to learn and then teach about them all but it would also be a lot for the students. I am not

saying that we need to not teach anything about other cultures at all. It definitely is important to educate students about the various cultures around the world. We just need to be choosy as to which ones so as not to overwhelm ourselves or the students.

Olive also reflects on the emotional weight of addressing sensitive topics in the classroom, writing that “[t]hese topics are heavy and they take time to reflect and digest. I feel a guilt and heaviness as I understand the impact that these topics have, yet know that these can all be challenging issues to develop in our classrooms with the high demands teachers have.”

These reflections reveal how rationalizing discourses, primarily mathematical-related ones, serve as a form of resistance, shaped by both genuine challenges and the perception of insurmountable obstacles. Addressing this resistance requires systemic support, intentional professional development, and collaborative strategies to help PPTs integrate CRP into their classrooms effectively and sustainably.

Pedagogical Resistance. Pedagogical resistance was primarily noticed as resistance to pedagogical change, often arising from PPTs’ attachment to traditional teaching methods or skepticism about the efficacy of new approaches. This form of resistance is rooted in a belief that the current pedagogical methods are effective, making CRP seem unnecessary or impractical. It may also include disbelief in the effectiveness of CRP itself. Some PPTs defend the status quo, questioning why CRP is necessary when traditional methods have proven successful in their experience. This sentiment, as illustrated in Table 2, is often expressed as, “Why CRP since we know that our methods work well?” Others remain unconvinced about CRP’s potential impact, asserting, “I’m not convinced it works.”

Felix reflects on the challenges of implementing CRP incrementally and the balance between traditional practices and new approaches, stating,

I have long held that many of the ideals proposed in our TESM certificate are lofty and challenging to put into practice and that an acceptable approach is to start small and build towards larger and more encompassing inclusion over time. So, I was heartened to read a practitioner and researcher sharing that there is in fact a balanced approach between explicit CM [critical mathematics] and SJ [social justice] oriented lessons and more ‘regular’ lesson and practice work.

Raymond expresses enthusiasm for critical mathematics but notes the comfort it brings because it aligns with his existing practices and, in the end, does not respond to his learners in what may be considered culturally responsive:

The topic that’s most exciting for me is Critical Mathematics. It’s easy to imagine how adventurous and exciting it could be to have students investigate justice issues in their neighborhood and beyond using the math tools they’ve been learning in K-12. I think the reason this is appealing is because I can imagine topics that could be explored (wealth inequality, fair trade, racial issues) and can even imagine the kinds of math students might need in order to investigate these topics (gathering/sorting/plotting data, functions and regression functions, areas under curves, measures of central tendency, and so on). AND I can imagine students might feel an emotional connection to the math that makes it engaging. On the other hand, I worry that the reason this is appealing is because it’s the closest thing to what I’m already doing, and therefore requires the least possible change of me. Moving to a Critical Math model through occasional inquiry activities could allow me

to still put my math goal first; and I notice that this doesn't necessarily involve my responding culturally to the specific learners in my classroom and their specific cultures or backgrounds.

Iris reflects on the challenges of adopting CRP, particularly for PPTs who were not exposed to it during their own education:

I certainly found some of the suggestions overwhelming. It's funny, a lot of the feedback from some of the seminars have been that people would like to see some sort of template or framework for helping develop us as CRP teachers. Yet, we've been provided a framework along with the reflective questions and here I am, feeling overwhelmed! I have this sense (not sure if it's grounded in any knowledge outside of my participation in this class), that CRP will not come as 'naturally' to educators until the educators who experience CRP as students, are in the classroom in the teacher role. I see teachers teach exactly how they learned in school (which makes sense, you know what you know!).

These reflections illustrate how resistance to pedagogical change can stem from a belief in the effectiveness of current methods, skepticism about CRP's impact, or the challenges of navigating new frameworks.

Ideological Resistance. Resistance to CRP can also stem from ideological dispositions, such as beliefs about the nature of mathematics, diversity, or education as a whole. This form of resistance is rooted in deeply held convictions and may manifest as resistance to ideological change, beliefs in the cultural neutrality of mathematics, or disbelief in the purposes of CRP. Resistance to ideological change occurs when PPTs are unwilling to alter their existing beliefs about the importance or relevance of diversity in education. This form of resistance, as illustrated in Table 2, is often expressed as, "We shouldn't change our ways because of people's diverse backgrounds." Similarly, some teachers view mathematics as inherently neutral, separate from cultural contexts or influences. Statements like "Mathematics is mathematics" reflect this belief. Others resist CRP because they fail to see its applicability, stating, "My students don't have diverse backgrounds; I don't see the point in this."

Cindy explains her skepticism about the integration of ethnomathematics in classrooms, saying,

I do not think if my math classes had been informed by ethnomathematics and language diversity much would have been different. I feel as if learning about other cultures in math would have not been meet well by my classmates as even learning about other cultures in history (a place where it was expected), my class did not take to it well to begin with. It was easier for my teacher to just go on as if nothing was different. In fact, it was easier that way as it was what we all expected, so even if she had incorporated some learning from an ethnomathematics point of view, she may have received some pushback from us as high school students.

She continues by suggesting an alternative approach to incorporating cultural content, saying,

There definitely is a time and a place in my opinion to bring in the math of other cultures. Math class is definitely one place to do that but... we can be culturally appropriate as well as culturally inclusive by incorporating math into social studies. Social studies would allow

us the flexibility to incorporate concepts from math into what is currently being studied. I feel that it would take some of the pressure away and allow students to see that math is found in more than just math class.

Olive reflects on the skepticism she encountered when discussing CRP in mathematics, sharing, “Initially, when I shared the title of the course, ‘Culturally Responsive Pedagogy in Mathematics,’ I had many teachers state that the two are not connected. I was skeptical towards the connection at first as well.”

Reflecting on his own growth and how ideological resistance can manifest in classroom interactions, Felix explains,

Overall, being more open and listening more actively to students expressing their own cultural and personal connections is an area to improve for me. I have reflected on a number of in-class conversations where students shared their own cultural perspective and instead of encouraging and incorporating, I essentially said ‘that’s nice!’ and focused back on ‘our’ learning.

As these quotes illustrate, ideological resistance can act as a barrier to the effective implementation of CRP. Rooted in beliefs about mathematics and education, this resistance underlines the importance of fostering openness, promoting professional development that challenges existing epistemological views, and creating supportive environments where PPTs can explore and adopt more inclusive practices.

Discussion

Our findings regarding fears and resistance are deeply intertwined with established research in teacher education and culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP), extending and affirming issues discussed in prior literature. The fears articulated by PPTs in our study – spanning mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological dimensions – are consistent with the anxieties described by Breen (2001) and Vithal (2003), who noted the prevalence of teachers’ fear of incompetence and failure. This is particularly salient in mathematics teacher education, where fears of insufficient subject-matter knowledge and inadequate preparation often intersect, as Lutovac and Kaasila (2014) highlight. Similarly, pedagogical fears regarding the complexities of implementation mirror the struggles outlined by Ashton and Arlington (2019), who emphasized the challenges PPTs face when translating theoretical knowledge into practical, responsive classroom strategies. Ideological fears, including concerns about cultural insensitivity, appropriation, or misrepresentation, align with the apprehensions noted by colleagues such as Gay and Howard (2000) and Meyer et al. (2019), who identified a widespread lack of preparation for teaching diverse student populations. For instance, Olive’s reflection in our data about her fear of tokenism echoes Meyer et al.’s (2019) findings that fears of missteps often lead teachers to avoid addressing diversity altogether. Moreover, Iris’s concerns about her Eurocentric worldview and its impact on her teaching effectiveness emphasize the identity-related tensions explored by Griffin (2015) and Shoyer and Leshem (2016). These fears, compounded by the unpredictability of classroom situations (Ashton & Arlington, 2019; Robinson & Goodey, 2018), reveal the intricate interplay between personal identity, professional readiness, and the socio-political dynamics of teaching.

Resistance was also discussed in this paper through the three main categories of mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological. These findings build on Rodriguez’s (2005a) exploration of resistance to ideological and pedagogical shifts in teacher education. The rationalizing discourses associated

with mathematics and mathematics curriculum observed in our participants – such as systemic constraints, feasibility concerns, and externalizing challenges (“it’s not me, it’s them”) – align closely with the systemic barriers highlighted by Hsieh and Nguyen (2021) and Bronkhorst et al. (2014). Olive’s reference to the pressures of meeting mandated curricula reflects the curriculum-related constraints detailed by scholars like Nicol (2006) and Tatto et al. (2006). These externalizing strategies not only shield PPTs from self-accountability but also reveal the structural challenges that impede the integration of CRP into mathematics education. The ideological resistance observed in our participants, particularly the belief in the cultural neutrality of mathematics (“mathematics is mathematics”), reinforces the epistemological challenges identified by Rose and Potts (2011) and Rodriguez (2005b). Such beliefs perpetuate a view of mathematics as a universal, context-free discipline, thereby undermining efforts to situate it within diverse cultural and social contexts. Cindy’s skepticism about the integration of ethnomathematics in her classroom reflects the broader ideological resistance described by LaDuke (2009) and Thomas and Vanderhaaro (2008), where teachers question the relevance of diversity-focused approaches in mathematics education. Resistance to pedagogical change, often rooted in comfort with traditional methods and skepticism about CRP’s effectiveness, is also consistent with the findings of Stoehr (2017) and McGlynn-Stewart (2010), who noted teachers’ reluctance to deviate from established practices, particularly in high-stakes subjects like mathematics.

Our findings not only reaffirm these established patterns but also extend them by offering refinements to our COFRI framework for analyzing the nuanced intersections between fear and resistance in teacher education. For example, Felix’s acknowledgment of his struggle to balance traditional practices with CRP-oriented approaches highlights the need for gradual, scaffolded professional development, as advocated by Brown (2014) and Aguirre et al. (2012). Similarly, Iris’s reflections on the generational shift required for CRP to ‘come naturally’ to teachers resonate with the long-term systemic change Baily and Katradis (2016) propose. By situating these insights within the COFRI framework, our study provides a more granular understanding of how fears and resistance operate not only as barriers but also as entry points for transformative growth when appropriately addressed. Our work contributes to the broader discourse on teacher education by illustrating how fears and resistance can be mitigated through intentional, reflective practices and systemic support. We underline the importance of addressing fears and resistance holistically, creating environments where PPTs can confront these challenges constructively. The COFRI framework offers a valuable tool for guiding such efforts, fostering the development of culturally responsive mathematics teachers who are equipped to navigate the complexities of contemporary classrooms. Within this spirit, we conclude this paper with some practical implications of our work for teacher education.

Implications

Our ongoing analysis for this research study— first introducing (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023a) and applying (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023b) our full COFRI framework, followed by a focus on the component of insights (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023c) and now on fears and resistance— aims to highlight how the dynamics of the COFRI components influence teachers’ readiness and capacity to engage with CRP. Our findings suggest that addressing these dynamics requires strategies that go beyond addressing individual fears or resistance. Instead, there is a need for holistic approaches that integrate reflective practices, peer collaboration, and structured opportunities to connect theoretical frameworks with practical applications.

Our discussion here highlights two key implications of the findings of this paper. First, we present revised definitions of fear and resistance, taking another step forward toward a fully revised

and comprehensive COFRI framework. Drawing on our analyses, in Table 3 we offer these revised definitions for fear and resistance toward refining the COFRI framework. Second, we draw on our findings to design reflective tools—one focused on fears in CRP and the other on resistance to CRP—that can be introduced by MTEs and used by PPTs as they learn about/with CRP.

<i>Characteristic</i>	[Original] Brief Description	Addition to Description
<i>Fear</i>	The feeling that attempting something might lead to failure. A person might be inclined to stop in their tracks (or even move backward), and to rationalise this (non)movement by saying they do not have (and cannot easily obtain) the KDST to achieve it.	The COFRI component of fear can be divided into three main types (and corresponding categories) of fear: mathematical (e.g., insufficient knowledge, inadequate preparation), pedagogical (e.g., inadequate implementation, complexity, causing harm), and ideological (e.g., cultural appropriation, cultural insensitivity, misrepresentation)
<i>Resistance</i>	The expression of dispositions against or disbelief in the importance, feasibility, or possibility of specific ideas. Resistance can manifest itself through “rationalising discourses” which have the property of projecting how <i>others</i> will act or respond to a situation—an “it’s not me, it’s them” approach to resisting an idea.	The COFRI component of resistance can be divided into three main types (and corresponding categories) of resistance: mathematical (e.g., projection, systemic constraints, feasibility, lack of resources), pedagogical (e.g., traditional methods, effectiveness), and ideological (e.g., change, cultural neutrality, relevance). In practice, these types often overlap, as a single statement of resistance may reflect more than one type at the same time.

Table 3. Revised Definitions for Fear and Resistance

Reflecting on and interpreting our findings has provided us with the motivation to design two reflective tools for PPTs: one to address fear and one to address resistance. The tools we present here offer ways for PPTs, who may presently be impeded by their fears and resistance to CRP, to face these issues and move forward in their own growth and development as culturally responsive mathematics teachers. By acknowledging their fears and resistance, and addressing them honestly and openly, PPTs can grow toward a strong and clear sociopolitical consciousness in mathematics education.

PPTs can engage with the tools we present here by selecting a statement that rings true for them in their own personal learning context, to first reflect on it by explaining how/why it is true for them, followed by a plan of action that could be implemented toward changing ones’ perspective on the statement. In this way—encouraging both reflection and action—we refer to the tools as reflective ‘praxis’ tools.

Fears. Our findings outline three categories of fears that we identified in the research data: **mathematical**, **pedagogical**, and **ideological**. While understanding and addressing each category on its own may prove valuable, the reflective ‘praxis’ tool for fear that we present here has softened the lines between these categories to reach greater holistic potential for the tool. Thus,

the statements presented in Figure 2 cut across the three categories of fears. Once a PPT selects a statement in Figure 2, they would make use of Table 4 to construct their reflection and action plan.

FEAR Statement	Reflection on why I selected this statement.	Action plan toward changing my perspective on the statement.

Table 4. A Praxis Tool to Address my FEARS about Teaching & Learning Mathematics through CRP

Figure 2. Fears about Teaching and Learning Mathematics Through CRP

Resistance. Our findings categorize PPTs' resistance as being **mathematical, pedagogical** or **ideological** forms of resistance. As noted with the fear praxis tool, while it may be valuable to understand and address each category on its own, the reflective 'praxis' tool for resistance that we present here has softened the lines between these categories to reach greater holistic potential for the tool. Thus, the statements presented in Figure 3 cut across the three categories of resistance. Once a PPT selects a statement in Figure 3, they would make use of Table 5 to construct their reflection and action plan.

RESISTANCE Statement	Reflection on why I selected this statement.	Action plan toward changing my perspective on the statement.

Table 5. A Praxis Tool to Address my RESISTANCE to Teaching & Learning Mathematics through CRP

Figure 3. Resistance to Teaching and Learning Mathematics through CRP

Conclusion

In this paper, we have aimed to advance understandings of CRP in mathematics education and to offer strategies for supporting teachers in navigating the fears and resistance that often arise. Through refinement of the COFRI framework and the introduction of reflective praxis tools, we hope to provide mathematics teacher educators and PPTs with more practical ways of addressing these complex affective experiences. The tools presented here—statements of fear and resistance, coupled with prompts for reflection and action—are shared for the first time and are expected to evolve as they are used in mathematics teacher education contexts.

Like any study, ours has limitations: because our data were drawn from reflective journals, our analysis centered mainly on PPTs' perspectives and affective reactions, leaving less visible how these fears and resistances may be experienced by their students or by teacher educators who carry the responsibility of supporting PPTs through such tensions. We see the reflective tools as one way to address this gap, since they encourage PPTs not only to recognize their own fears and resistance but also to consider how these reactions may ripple outward to shape the experiences of others. The importance of this attention is emphasized in the literature, with several studies showing that teachers' apprehension or anxiety about mathematics often leads them to adopt more rigid, rule-based practices, transferring their unease to students (see, e.g., Golafshani, 2013; Hart & Swars, 2009; Hodgen & Askew, 2007). Breaking this cycle requires a shift in how teachers understand both mathematics and their relationship to/with it (Lowery, 2002; Samuelsson, 2023), and our reflective praxis tools are designed to support such shifts by creating space for PPTs to surface and interrogate their affective responses in constructive ways. Future research will continue to refine these tools and examine how they can illuminate not only the perspectives of PPTs but also the experiences of students and teacher educators, thereby contributing to a more layered understanding of fear and resistance toward developing one's CRP in mathematics teacher

education and supporting the development of culturally responsive practices across all levels of teaching and learning.

Afterword: Authors' Reflections

For the research study and analysis described in this paper, our point of departure was Gloria Ladson-Billings' articulation of culturally *relevant* pedagogy. While analyzing data from a Canadian mathematics teacher education course (where CRP represented culturally *responsive* pedagogy), we found that prospective and practicing teachers' (PPTs') reflections did not fit neatly within Ladson-Billings' three CRP elements or their combinations. From these tensions, COFRI emerged as a way of naming and organizing aspects of teacher learning that were not fully visible in existing literature. Although COFRI builds on Ladson-Billings' foundational contributions, it also departs from them by foregrounding the affective and often contradictory dimensions of teachers' engagements with CRP in mathematics. Within COFRI, the components of fear and resistance illustrate both the value and the limits of analytic distinctions. Fears could be organized fairly readily into mathematical, pedagogical, and ideological types. Resistance, on the other hand, was harder to sort; while the same three types were present, they appeared in mixed and overlapping ways. We take this not as a shortcoming of the framework but as a reflection of how resistance operates: drawing on multiple, intersecting justifications at once, and thereby revealing the complexity of PPTs' negotiations with CRP.

The open review process was instrumental in sharpening this perspective. Our reviewer, Tonya Bartell, encouraged us to treat overlaps as central rather than marginal. Her comments pushed us to recognize entanglement as a defining strength of COFRI: the framework not only highlights useful distinctions but also makes room for moments when clarity dissolves into complexity. Just as importantly, the open review process itself humanized academic publishing. Instead of receiving anonymous reports in writing, we engaged with Tonya's written review feedback through email correspondence and a Zoom conversation with her. This gave us the opportunity to interact with a respected colleague in the field, to ask questions, and to see our work from vantage points we might not have otherwise considered. That interaction reinforced the idea that scholarship is a collaborative endeavour, one that benefits from openness and dialogue as much as from critique. The editor-in-chief, David Bowers (they/them), also played a critical role, continually pressing us to be more reflective about our own framing. Their feedback reminded us that analytic categories are never neutral: they shape what researchers notice, delimit what is considered significant, and carry both risks and possibilities. This insistence on reflexivity helped us refine COFRI into a framework that is at once descriptive and critical.

Looking ahead, our intention is to continue developing COFRI as both an analytic and pedagogical resource. To this end, we are designing reflective tools to accompany each component, supporting PPTs in examining their own perspectives in relation to culturally responsive pedagogy. Future iterations of the course will allow us to further refine these tools in practice, with and for PPTs, as we learn how they function to open dialogue, surface tensions, and foster reflexivity. In this spirit, we view COFRI not as a fixed product but as an evolving framework. Our hope is that colleagues in mathematics education and beyond will take it up, adapt it to their contexts, and challenge its assumptions. In doing so, we believe the framework can catalyze continued dialogue about the complex and sometimes contradictory realities of preparing teachers for CRP.

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